

hdWGCNA_fun_enrichments

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Description

All code required to generate gene co-expression modules from the Herring et al prefrontal cortex snRNAseq data and complete enrichment analysis.

Required packages

```
library(pacman)
p_unload(dplyr)
p_load(Seurat, tidyverse, WGCNA, hdWGCNA, clusterProfiler, gplots,
       gridExtra)
p_load(dplyr) #ensure always loaded last
```

Preparation of seurat object

```
# read matrix and metadata
metadata <- readRDS("snRNAseq_data/listerlab_pfc/listerlab_pfc_metadata.RDS")
counts <- readRDS(file = "snRNAseq_data/listerlab_pfc/gene_count_duplicategenescombined.RDS")

seurat <- CreateSeuratObject(counts = counts, meta.data = metadata,
                             min.cells = 1, min.features = 1)
seurat <- NormalizeData(seurat)
seurat <- FindVariableFeatures(seurat, selection.method = "vst",
                              nfeatures = 2000)
seurat <- ScaleData(seurat)
seurat <- RunPCA(seurat, features = VariableFeatures(object = seurat))
seurat <- RunUMAP(seurat, dims = 1:30)
seurat <- FindNeighbors(seurat, dims = 1:30)
seurat <- FindClusters(seurat, resolution = 1.5)
saveRDS(seurat, "results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/SeuratReadyForhdWGCNA.RDS")
rm(list = ls())
```

Read in seurat object. Remove poor-quality cells.

```

seurat <- readRDS("../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/output_not_subset/SeuratReadyForhdWGCNA.RDS")
# Define the output directory
output_dir <- "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs"
# Use showWarnings to suppress warnings if the directory
# already exists
dir.create(output_dir, recursive = TRUE, showWarnings = FALSE)
# creates a vector specifying the groups to use for
# metacells. First element of vector refers to the 'main'
# grouping variable, i.e. the ident, second element of
# vector specifies any other variables sampling variables
group <- c("metadata$stage_id")
Idents(seurat) <- "stage_id" # set the idents of the Seurat object
seurat <- subset(seurat, subset = major_clust != "Poor-Quality")

```

The function: by cell type.

```

# Get unique major_clust values
unique_clusters <- unique(seurat$major_clust)
levels(unique_clusters)

# Define a function to perform analysis for each cluster
perform_analysis_for_cluster <- function(cluster_seurat, cluster_name) {
  # Create a directory for the current cluster
  cluster_output_dir <- file.path(paste0(output_dir, "/", cluster_name))
  dir.create(cluster_output_dir, recursive = TRUE, showWarnings = FALSE)

  ##### Determine which genes to use for hdWGCNA
  message("Setting up for WGCNA (", Sys.time(), ")") # message for clarity
  cluster_seurat <- SetupForWGCNA(seurat_obj = cluster_seurat, # the seurat object
    gene_select = "fraction", # the gene selection approach
    fraction = 0.05, # fraction of cells that a gene needs to be
    #expressed in to be included
    wgcna_name = "hdWGCNA" # the name of the hdWGCNA experiment
  )

  ##### construct metacells

  message("Constructing metacells (", Sys.time(), ")")

  cluster_seurat <- MetacellsByGroups(
    seurat_obj = cluster_seurat, # seurat object
    group.by = c("stage_id"), # specify the columns in seurat_obj@meta.data to group by
    reduction = "pca", # select the dimensionality reduction to perform KNN on
    k = 50, # nearest-neighbors parameter
    max_shared = 30, # maximum number of shared cells between two metacells
    ident.group = "stage_id" # set the Idents of the metacell seurat object
  )

  ##### Normalize metacells
  message("Normalizing metacells (", Sys.time(), ")")
  cluster_seurat <- NormalizeMetacells(cluster_seurat)

```

```

##### define expression dataset. Assume sctransform is not used.

cluster_seurat <- SetDatExpr(cluster_seurat,
                             assay = 'RNA', # using RNA assay
                             slot = 'data' # using normalized data
                             )

##### Test appropriate soft power for network construction
message("Testing soft powers (", Sys.time(), ")")

# Determine what soft power threshold to use
cluster_seurat <- TestSoftPowers(cluster_seurat,
                                 networkType = 'signed') # you can also use "unsigned" or "signed hybrid"

##### Construct the coexpression network

message("Constructing network (", Sys.time(), ")")

cluster_seurat <- ConstructNetwork(
  cluster_seurat,
  setDatExpr=FALSE,
  tom_outdir = paste0(output_dir,"/", cluster_name), # where to write the TOM
  tom_name = "TOM",
  overwrite_tom = TRUE # name of the topological overlap matrix written to disk
)

# soft power is automatically selected based on results of TestSoftPowers.
# we can also validate this choice later.

cluster_seurat@meta.data$major_clust <- droplevels(cluster_seurat@meta.data$major_clust)
pdf(paste0(output_dir,"/", cluster_name,"/",cluster_name, "_dendrogram.pdf"))
PlotDendrogram(cluster_seurat, main = "hdWGCNA dendrogram")

dev.off()

##### Compute module eigengenes
message("Computing MEs (", Sys.time(), ")")
cluster_seurat <- ScaleData(cluster_seurat, features=VariableFeatures(cluster_seurat))

# compute all MEs in the full single-cell dataset
cluster_seurat <- ModuleEigengenes(cluster_seurat)
cluster_seurat <- ModuleConnectivity(cluster_seurat)
# save seurat object here..
saveRDS(cluster_seurat,paste0(output_dir,"/", cluster_name,"/",cluster_name,"Module_connectivity.RDS"))

MEs <- GetMEs(cluster_seurat) %>%
  dplyr::select(!grey) # Retrieve ME information

metadata.celltypes <- cluster_seurat@meta.data %>%
  dplyr::select(stage_id) %>%
  rownames_to_column(var = "sample") # begin by processing metadata

```

```

MEs.edited <- MEs %>%
  rownames_to_column(var = "sample") %>%
  left_join(metadata.celltypes,
            by = "sample") # append metadata to ME information

# Next is to extract information specific for each module

ME.cell.associations <- list() # initialize empty list
ME.cell.associations <- lapply(colnames(MEs),
  FUN = function(x){
    df <- MEs.edited %>%
      dplyr::select(any_of(x), sample, stage_id) %>%
        # only look at one module at a time
        arrange(desc(get(x))) %>% # the value under each module is the ME.
          #This arranges the dataframe by descending order of MEs
          slice_head(n = 100)# extract the top n entries
    ME.cell.associations[[x]] <- df
    # append the created dataframe to the object
  })

names(ME.cell.associations) <- colnames(MEs) # Assigns names to each data frame,

##### Next create a list of ggplot objects.
#Each plot in the list corresponds to a different module.
p <- lapply(1:ncol(MEs), function(x){ # Iterate over each column - I specify index.
  module_name <- names(ME.cell.associations)[[x]] # Determine the module name

  cat("Processing module:", module_name, "\n")

  data <- ME.cell.associations[[x]] %>%
    group_by(stage_id) %>%
    summarise(n = n()) %>%
    arrange(n) %>% # arrange the data frame based on which

    # Define levels for major_clust
    mutate(stage_id = factor(stage_id, levels = stage_id)) # needed for reordering

  # Print intermediate results for debugging
  cat("Module Name:", module_name, "\n")
  cat("First few rows of data:\n")
  print(head(data))
  cat("Unique values of major_clust:\n")
  print(unique(data$stage_id))

  # Construct plot now
  cat("Processing module:", module_name, "\n")

  p <- ggplot(data = data, aes(x = n, y = data$stage_id)) +
    geom_segment(aes(yend = data$stage_id, xend = 0)) + # geom_segment adds lines
    geom_point(size = 4, color = module_name) + # geom_point adds points. In combination with
    theme_bw() +
    ggtitle(paste0("Module ", module_name, " stage distribution")) +
    xlab("Number of cells") +

```

```

        ylab(paste0(data$stage_id, " type") )
    })

# Save the output to pdf

ggsave(paste0(output_dir, "/hdWGCNA_ModuleCellDistribution_", cluster_name, ".pdf"),
        plot = marrangeGrob(p,
                            nrow = 1,
                            ncol = 1),
        height = 7,
        width = 11)

##### Prepare input data
message("Running enrichment analysis (", Sys.time(), ")")
MEs <- GetMEs(cluster_seurat) %>%
  dplyr::select(!grey) # Retrieves the ME values

phenotype_to_genes <- read_tsv("../HPO_dat/phenotype_to_genes.txt")
id_to_name <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  dplyr::select(hpo_id, hpo_name) %>%
  distinct() # creates dataframe specifying HPO ID and name associations

id_to_gene <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  dplyr::select(hpo_id, ncbi_gene_id) %>%
  distinct() #creates dataframe specifying associations between gene and HPO IDs.

# prepare the background
background <- cluster_seurat@misc$hdWGCNA$wgcn_genes
# all the genes used for WGCNA will be used as background

# Data includes the genelists to be enriched.
genelist <- list() # initialize empty list
# this function creates a list of vectors containing the genes found in each module
genelist <- sapply(colnames(MEs), function(x){

  genes <- cluster_seurat@misc$hdWGCNA$wgcn_modules %>%
    filter(module == x) %>%
    pull(gene_name)
  genelist <- append(genelist, list(genes))
})

names(genelist) <- colnames(MEs) #changes names of each vector in list,
#allowing clusters to be named
set.seed(42)

message("Running comparecluster on HPO terms (", Sys.time(), ")")
tryCatch({
  ck <- compareCluster(geneClusters = genelist, # performs the enrichment
                      fun = "enricher",
                      pvalueCutoff = 0.2,
                      qvalueCutoff = 0.2,
                      universe = background,
                      TERM2GENE = id_to_gene,

```

```

        TERM2NAME = id_to_name) %>%
setReadable(OrgDb = "org.Hs.eg.db",
            keyType = "ENTREZID")

##### Save enrichment results
#####
# remove enrichments with gene counts less than x
x <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%
    filter(Count >= 5)

# write out csv enrichments
write_csv(x, paste0(output_dir, "/HPO_enrichments_", cluster_name, ".csv"))
})

##### Repeat above with GO BP terms
message("Running comparecluster on GO BP terms (", Sys.time(), ")")

tryCatch({
  ck <- compareCluster(geneClusters= genelist,
                      fun = "enrichGO",
                      OrgDb = "org.Hs.eg.db",
                      pAdjustMethod = "BH",
                      pvalueCutoff = 0.2,
                      qvalueCutoff = 0.2,
                      universe = background,
                      readable = TRUE,
                      ont = "BP")

  x <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%
      filter(Count >= 5)

  write_csv(x, paste0(output_dir, "/GO_enrichments_", cluster_name, "_BP.csv"))

})

##### Repeat above with GO CC terms
message("Running comparecluster on GO CC terms (", Sys.time(), ")")
tryCatch({
  ck <- compareCluster(geneClusters= genelist,
                      fun = "enrichGO",
                      OrgDb = "org.Hs.eg.db",
                      pAdjustMethod = "BH",
                      pvalueCutoff = 0.2,
                      qvalueCutoff = 0.2,
                      universe = background,
                      readable = TRUE,
                      ont = "CC")

  x <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%
      filter(Count >= 5)

```

```

write_csv(x, paste0(output_dir, "/GO_enrichments_", cluster_name, "_CC.csv"))
})

##### Repeat above with GO MF terms
message("Running comparecluster on GO MF terms (", Sys.time(), ")")
tryCatch({
  ck <- compareCluster(geneClusters= genelist,
                      fun = "enrichGO",
                      OrgDb = "org.Hs.eg.db",
                      pAdjustMethod = "BH",
                      pvalueCutoff = 0.2,
                      qvalueCutoff = 0.2,
                      universe = background,
                      readable = TRUE,
                      ont = "MF")

  x <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%
    filter(Count >= 5)

  write_csv(x, paste0(output_dir, "/GO_enrichments_", cluster_name, "_MF.csv"))
})
})
}

```

Run the function:

```

# Iterate through each unique major_clust and perform
# analysis
for (cluster_name in unique_clusters) {
  cluster_seurat <- subset(seurat, subset = major_clust ==
                          cluster_name)
  perform_analysis_for_cluster(cluster_seurat, cluster_name)
}

while (!is.null(dev.list())) dev.off()

```

a method of running enrichment analysis outside of the function; utilise saved ModuleConnectivity .RDS files

```

outdir <- "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/"
celltypes <- list.dirs(path = outdir, full.names = FALSE, recursive = FALSE)

```

Note, in this code chunk we save all enrichments regardless of padj values to enable us to calculate CLR Z-scores

```

for(cell in celltypes) {
  cluster_seurat <- readRDS(paste0(outdir, cell, "/", cell, "Module_connectivity.RDS"))
  ##### Prepare input data
  MEs <- GetMEs(cluster_seurat) %>%
    dplyr::select(!grey) # Retrieves the ME values

```

```

# Next prepare the background all the genes used for WGCNA will be used as BG
background <- cluster_seurat@misc$hdWGCNA$wgcna_genes
# Data includes the genelists to be enriched.
genelist <- list() # initialize empty list
#this function creates a list of vectors containing the genes found in each module
genelist <- sapply(colnames(MEs), function(x){

  genes <- cluster_seurat@misc$hdWGCNA$wgcna_modules %>%
    filter(module == x) %>%
    pull(gene_name)
  genelist <- append(genelist, list(genes))
})

# changes names of each vector in list, allowing clusters to be named
names(genelist) <- colnames(MEs)
set.seed(42)
##### DGN terms
message("Running comparecluster on DisGeNET terms (", Sys.time(), ")")

ck <- compareCluster(geneClusters = genelist,
  fun = "enrichDGN",
  pAdjustMethod = "BH",
  pvalueCutoff = 1.5,
  qvalueCutoff = 1.5,
  universe = background,
  readable = TRUE)

enrichments <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%
  mutate(Cluster = as.character(Cluster))
enrichments$Cluster <- paste0(cell, "_", enrichments$Cluster)
write_csv(enrichments, paste0(outdir, cell, "/DGN_enrichments_all_", cell, "_DGN", ".csv"))

# repeat for HPO enrichments
phenotype_to_genes <- read_tsv("../HPO_dat/phenotype_to_genes.txt")
id_to_name <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  dplyr::select(hpo_id, hpo_name) %>%
  distinct() # creates dataframe specifying HPO ID and name associations

id_to_gene <- phenotype_to_genes %>%
  dplyr::select(hpo_id, ncbi_gene_id) %>%
  distinct() # creates dataframe specifying associations between gene and HPO IDs.

ck <- compareCluster(geneClusters = genelist, # performs the enrichment
  fun = "enricher",
  pvalueCutoff = 1.5,
  qvalueCutoff = 1.5,
  universe = background,
  TERM2GENE = id_to_gene,
  TERM2NAME = id_to_name) %>%
  setReadable(OrgDb = "org.Hs.eg.db",
    keyType = "ENTREZID")

enrichments <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%

```

```

mutate(Cluster = as.character(Cluster))
enrichments$Cluster <- paste0(cell, "_", enrichments$Cluster)
write_csv(enrichments, paste0(outdir, cell, "/HPO_enrichments_all_", cell, "_HPO", ".csv"))
}

```

calculating CLR Z-scores: First combine cell-specific enrichment .csvs

```

#####GO MF#####
outdir <- "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/"

result <- system2(command = "find", # system2 allows us to run command line arguments in R.
                 args = c(outdir,
                          "-type", "f",
                          "-name", "'*_MF.csv'"),
                 stdout = TRUE,
                 stderr = TRUE)
# this creates a data frame specifying the paths to my enrichment csvs,
# as well as the cell type each enrichment csv is associated with.
result_df <- data.frame(path = result,
                       celltype = str_remove_all(result,
                                                  paste0(outdir, "/"))) %>%

  separate_wider_delim(cols = celltype,
                      delim = "/",
                      names = c("celltype", "remove")) %>%

  select(path, celltype)

data_list <- map(result, ~ {
  # Extract cell type from the filename
  celltype <- sub("^(.*)_enrichments.csv$", "\\1", basename(.x))
  df <- read_csv(.x)
})

# Naming the list elements
names(data_list) <- result_df$celltype

# Data manipulation using purrr and dplyr
data_list <- imap(data_list, ~ .x %>%
                 group_by(ID) %>%
                 #filter(Count >= 5) %>%
                 ungroup()
)

combined_df <- bind_rows(data_list)
write_csv(combined_df,
          "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/all_celltypes_GO_MF_enrichments.csv")

#####Repeat for GO BP: #####
outdir <- "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/"

result <- system2(command = "find", # system2 allows us to run command line arguments in R.
                 args = c(outdir,
                          "-type", "f",

```

```

        "-name", "'*_BP.csv'"),
        stdout = TRUE,
        stderr = TRUE)

result_df <- data.frame(path = result,
                        celltype = str_remove_all(result,
                                                    paste0(outdir, "/"))) %>%

  separate_wider_delim(cols = celltype,
                       delim = "/",
                       names = c("celltype", "remove")) %>%
  select(path, celltype)

data_list <- map(result, ~ {
  # Extract cell type from the filename
  celltype <- sub("^(.*)_enrichments.csv$", "\\1", basename(.x))
  df <- read_csv(.x)
})

# Naming the list elements
names(data_list) <- result_df$celltype

# Data manipulation using purrr and dplyr
data_list <- imap(data_list, ~ .x %>%
  group_by(ID) %>%
  #filter(Count >= 5) %>%
  ungroup()
)

combined_df <- bind_rows(data_list)
write_csv(combined_df,
          "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/all_celltypes_GO_BP_enrichments.csv")

##### Repeat for GO CC#####

result <- system2(command = "find", # system2 allows us to run command line arguments in R.
                  args = c(outdir,
                            "-type", "f",
                            "-name", "'*_CC.csv'"),
                  stdout = TRUE,
                  stderr = TRUE)

result_df <- data.frame(path = result,
                        celltype = str_remove_all(result,
                                                    paste0(outdir, "/"))) %>%

  separate_wider_delim(cols = celltype,
                       delim = "/",
                       names = c("celltype", "remove")) %>%
  select(path, celltype)

data_list <- map(result, ~ {
  # Extract cell type from the filename
  celltype <- sub("^(.*)_enrichments.csv$", "\\1", basename(.x))

```

```

    df <- read_csv(.x)
  })

  # Naming the list elements
  names(data_list) <- result_df$celltype

  # Data manipulation using purrr and dplyr
  data_list <- imap(data_list, ~ .x %>%
    group_by(ID) %>%
    #filter(Count >= 5) %>%
    ungroup()
)

combined_df <- bind_rows(data_list)
write_csv(combined_df,
  "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/all_celltypes_GO_CC_enrichments.csv")

##### Repeat for HPO#####

result <- system2(command = "find", # system2 allows us to run command line arguments in R.
  args = c(outdir,
    "-type", "f",
    "-name", "'HPO_*.csv'"),
  stdout = TRUE,
  stderr = TRUE)

result_df <- data.frame(path = result,
  celltype = str_remove_all(result,
    paste0(outdir, "/"))) %>%

  separate_wider_delim(cols = celltype,
    delim = "/",
    names = c("celltype", "remove")) %>%
  select(path, celltype)

data_list <- map(result, ~ {
  # Extract cell type from the filename
  celltype <- sub("^(.*)_enrichments.csv$", "\\1", basename(.x))
  df <- read_csv(.x)
})

# Naming the list elements
names(data_list) <- result_df$celltype

# Data manipulation using purrr and dplyr
data_list <- imap(data_list, ~ .x %>%
  group_by(ID) %>%
  filter(Count >= 5) %>%
  ungroup()
)

combined_df <- bind_rows(data_list)

```

```

write_csv(combined_df,
          "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/all_celltypes_HPO_enrichments.csv")

#####DGN#####
outdir <- "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/"

result <- system2(command = "find", # system2 allows us to run command line arguments in R.
                  args = c(outdir,
                           "-type", "f",
                           "-name", "'*_DGN.csv'"),
                  stdout = TRUE,
                  stderr = TRUE)

result_df <- data.frame(path = result,
                       celltype = str_remove_all(result,
                                                  paste0(outdir, "/"))) %>%

  separate_wider_delim(cols = celltype,
                      delim = "/",
                      names = c("celltype", "remove")) %>%

  select(path, celltype)

data_list <- map(result, ~ {
  # Extract cell type from the filename
  celltype <- sub("^(.*)_enrichments.csv$", "\\1", basename(.x))
  df <- read_csv(.x)
})

# Naming the list elements
names(data_list) <- result_df$celltype

# Data manipulation using purrr and dplyr
data_list <- imap(data_list, ~ .x %>%
  group_by(ID) %>%
  # filter(Count >= 5) %>%
  ungroup()
)

combined_df <- bind_rows(data_list)
write_csv(combined_df,
          "../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/all_celltypes_DGN_enrichments.csv")

```

Next, run the CLR Z-score and save.

```

HPO <- read_csv("../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/all_celltypes_HPO_enrichments.csv")
DGN <- read_csv("../results/single_cell/hdWGCNA/celltype/outputs/all_celltypes_DGN_enrichments.csv")

# define CLR function
my_z_score <- function(x) {
  if (sd(x) == 0) {
    return(rep(0, length(x)))
  }
}

```

```

    } else {
      return((x - mean(x))/sd(x))
    }
  }

clr <- function(m) {
  z_scores_column <- apply(m, 2, function(x) my_z_score(x))
  z_scores_row <- t(apply(m, 1, function(x) my_z_score(x)))
  return(sqrt(z_scores_column^2 + z_scores_row^2))
}

```

HPO

```

# Here, I read in a "dummy" comparecluster object,
# then assign the HPO enrichments to the compareclusterresult slot
# before doing some manipulation.
ck <- readRDS("../..../Downloads/HPO_enrichments.RDS")
ck@compareClusterResult <- HPO
enrichments <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%
  mutate(Cluster = as.character(Cluster))

x <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%
  dplyr::select(Cluster, p.adjust, Description) %>%
  pivot_wider(names_from = Cluster,
              values_from = p.adjust) %>%
  column_to_rownames(var = "Description") %>%
  replace(is.na(.), 1) %>%
  as.matrix()

mat <- clr(x)
mat_long <- mat %>%
  as.data.frame(row.names = rownames(mat)) %>%
  rownames_to_column(var = "Description") %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = 2:ncol(.),
              names_to = "Cluster",
              values_to = "CLR.zscore")

full_results <- full_join(enrichments, mat_long)
full_res <- full_results %>%
  filter(Count >= 5) %>% # remove enrichments with gene counts less than x
  filter(p.adjust < 0.2)
##### Save enrichment results
write_csv(full_res, paste0(outdir, "/CLR_HPO_enrichments_allcells.csv"))

```

DGN

```

ck <- readRDS("../..../Downloads/HPO_enrichments.RDS")
ck@compareClusterResult <- DGN

enrichments <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%
  mutate(Cluster = as.character(Cluster))

x <- ck@compareClusterResult %>%

```

```

dplyr::select(Cluster, p.adjust, Description) %>%
pivot_wider(names_from = Cluster,
            values_from = p.adjust) %>%
column_to_rownames(var = "Description") %>%
replace(is.na(.), 1) %>%
as.matrix()

mat <- clr(x)
mat_long <- mat %>%
  as.data.frame(row.names = rownames(mat)) %>%
  rownames_to_column(var = "Description") %>%
  pivot_longer(cols = 2:ncol(.),
              names_to = "Cluster",
              values_to = "CLR.zscore")

full_results <- full_join(enrichments, mat_long)
full_res <- full_results %>%
  filter(Count >= 5) %>% # remove enrichments with gene counts less than x
  filter(p.adjust < 0.2)
##### Save enrichment results
write_csv(full_res, paste0(outdir, "/CLR_DGN_enrichments_allcells.csv"))

```